

FORMING APPROACHES TO LEARNING ENTREPRENEURIAL AND BUSINESS TERMS IN UZBEKI AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The article examines the sources and methods of studying entrepreneurship and business terms in Uzbek and English. Adapted approaches to the term business and entrepreneurship in the languages are shown.

Key words: business, entrepreneurship, languages, integration, term, linguistics, approach, formation

In the current globalized era, a number of studies are being conducted in linguistics due to the great attention given to the progress and development of science. As a result of the developments, various concepts have appeared in the lexical layer of the language, which require linguocultural study. It is known that all languages used in the world have different terms due to their characteristics, and terms are important for every aspect of our life. Terms are enriched in different ways depending on their nature.

In contrast to the above statements, there are a number of other definitions, which are as follows: "A term is a word that is limited by its specific and special signs: it is an unambiguous, clear word that is more often used in the fields of science, technology, economics, politics and diplomacy." V. P. Danilenko defines the word term in accordance with the mentioned Reformatsky's opinion as follows: "The term is considered a part of the vocabulary and is the exact name and definition of the lexical units of a certain science and field." In relation to ideas, in fact, the term refers to a number of areas that cannot be defined by a single word or phrase, and is a linguistic unit that expresses meaning in these areas. In addition to foreign linguists, many Uzbek scholars have expressed their opinions about the term. One of them is doctor of philology, G. Abdurahmanov writes: "The accuracy and consistency of terms shows the level of science, education, and culture of this nation. The development and regulation of terms varies in different fields of science and depends on the progress of a certain science. Since this progress is continuous, the origin and regulation of new terms is also continuous. In general, careful processing and arrangement of terms in the native language is a necessary resource for creating textbooks and manuals, as well as for teaching in the native language. The lack of processing and arrangement of terms also affects the style of speech." Therefore, the regulation

of terminology, the appropriate translation from one language to another is one of the important issues not only in the scientific field, but also in social life.

In English literature, it is interpreted as "a term is a word or phrase used to express a concept in a particular language or field of science." The Merriam-Webster dictionary defines a term as "a word or expression that has a specific meaning in a particular field, or is characteristic of a science, art, or professional activity" and terminology as "technical or special terms used in a business, art, science, or other specialized field." "Terminology-the special words and terms used in science, art, business and economy". It can be seen from the English-language sources that terms are widely used in social spheres. According to the statements of the cited linguists, in our opinion, the word "term" in a language is a word or a combination of words that is used only at a certain level and expresses the meaning of a certain word or phrase in a private sense and is related to fields such as economy, politics, business, entrepreneurship.

Since this period, a number of scientific studies on terms and terminology have been conducted. Currently, there are several foreign schools, in particular, the Austrian-German school, the French-Canadian school, the Russian school, and the Czech school, which approach the theoretical issues of terminology from different angles and find solutions to existing problems. It is worth noting that among them, the Russian School of Terminology is currently leading among other schools due to the fact that it researches current issues and achieves certain results in this field. More than 2,300 defended dissertations and more than 3,500 scientific works have studied terms as a proof of our statement. As can be seen from the figures, the term and terminology, their problems, cross-cultural research in different languages is one of the most relevant issues for modern linguistics.

Today, terminology is divided into a number of research directions, which we will discuss below. 1. "Theoretical terminology - studies the laws of development and use of special lexicons (terms); 2. Practical terminology - practical principles of terms, on eliminating the shortcomings of terms and terminology. deals with the development of recommendations, tools for their use, creation and translation; 3. General terminology - studies the general properties and problems of special lexicons (terms); 4. Special terminology - studies terms belonging to a specific field of a certain language; 5. Typological terminology - they compare separate terminologies and determine the properties of general and special terminology; 6. Hybrid terminology - studies the common and special terminology of different languages by combining them and brings out

their properties; 7. Semasiological terminology - problems related to the semantics of special lexemes, changes in semantic units, polysemy, studies synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy; 8. Onomastic terminology - studies special lexemes of naming, their naming process, choosing the optimal form of naming; 9. Historical terminology - studies the history of terminology and analyzes the origin and formation process of terms. This is how terms are regulated. Based on the results of this trend, a new independent science - anthropolinguistics - has emerged in linguistics; 10. Functional terminology - studies the functions of modern terms in various texts, in professional communication situations, in the training of specialists, as well as the features of using terms in speech and computer systems.

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